

Analysis of Factors Influencing on Quality of Pedagogical Basis of Active Teaching Practices in Private and Public Sectors of Bahawalpur, Pakistan

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Abstract:- South Punjab is least literate province of Pakistan and 54% are out of school children in Bahawalpur which is the main percentage in Pakistan. (Pakistan Social & Living Standards Measurements Survey PSLM/HIES 2018-19). The education system in Bahawalpur is separated into two categories: public and private. The research's main goal was to compare and analyze factors for pedagogical practices of Government and Private schools' teachers in Bahawalpur. Since there is scarcity of literature about teachers issues under study. This is quantitative design research. The data was collected from 9 private schools and 11 Government schools in the Bahawalpur district. Twenty-five (25) teachers were selected from each sample institute. A questionnaire was used to collect data. Data was examined through SPSS version 19. The data exposed a minor difference between private and government school teachers' pedagogical practices. These studies determined some consequences that quality of pedagogical practices of public education sector is not well than private-sector institutes. It was suggested that there should be joint ventures of private and government schools that may contain student educational activities or teachers' trainings which may create healthy learning environment. The quality of work-related life of teachers may be improved from beginning to end by resolving issues of teachers in workplace, providing proper pedagogical training to the teachers by revising the existing curriculum. Thus, job career satisfaction rate is high among private sector teachers than public. Working stress in private teaching institutes perceived low quality of pedagogy practices than public institutes. The conclusions will be beneficial for school administrators, curriculum developers, managers and policy makers.

Keywords:- Public School, Private School, Quality of Pedagogical Teaching Practices, Stress on Teachers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many researchers concluded that no nation can be progressed without education. If we notice five years educational policies stepped by governments in education, it was very imperative to mention that intent of every government was build an educated nation and education

should be accessible to all. In Pakistan, education spending has amplified at annual average rate of 10.5% since 2022. The current literacy rate is 62.3 according to the Ministry of Federal Education, which means that a predictable population of 60 million is uneducated in country. Private expenditure by parents is even higher than public spending with the total adding up to nearly 6% of GDP.

Moreover, school literacy and enrollment rates have remained neutral, illustrating that the primary cause is a corrupt system of political sponsorship. This method jeopardizes the country's future by creating ghost schools, ghost teachers, and absentee teaching staff to syphon off funds owed to students' education. Leaders should have to imitate on this fact and defend education from negative and destructive system of political sponsorship networks. (Haq, 2017)

When it comes to Bahawalpur the situation is even worsened 54% are out of school children which is the peak percentage in country. There are 1662 total schools and 24 are schools according to Punjab information technology board. There are 1186 Primary, 252 Middle, 30 Secondary schools in Bahawalpur Punjab district, (Pakistan Social & Living Standards Measurements Survey PSLM/HIES 2018-19). This paved the way for a modest number of teachers to emerge from the province, particularly women and teachers from remote areas. The pedagogical system in Bahawalpur is separated into 2 types public and private. Private schools are self-supporting and rely on fees collected from students. The bulk of them receive no financial assistance from the government or private organizations. Bahawalpur's general teaching system is divided into following categories 3 years of pre-school, 5 years of primary school, 3 years of middle school, 2 years of secondary school, and 2 years of upper secondary school, similar to private schools fascinate high proportion of all school-aged students. The trend of sending children to private schools is rapidly growing, with even the poorest parents wishing to send their children to private schools. (M.

➤ *Sheikh 2007)*

The advanced and traditional teaching training methods was using in different schools with maximum usage of technology in private schools and minimum usage in government schools due to absence of many facilities and

infrastructure available in government schools (Kumari Poonam, Singh Neetu. 2014). Another contrary results that public schools have proper infrastructure, qualified teaching staff, basic facilities and teaching quality as compared to private schools (Awan, Dr. Abdul., 2020). The quality of private schools is improved than government schools in terms of pedagogical methodology (Ali, Malik & Azam, Irsa & Ali, Kashif., 2020). The research gap in the literature regarding work quality of private and government school teachers. Therefore, the study was done to compare public and private schools using the most comprehensive pedagogical practices available in literature. Main goals of study were investigated of factors affecting on quality of pedagogical basis of active teaching practices in public and private sectors and comparison between government and private schools' teaching practices. The study is quantitative in nature using questionnaire developed by reviewing existing literature on pedagogical practices. The data was get-together from government and private schools' teachers. The results are significant for the curriculum developers and school authorities by giving an overview of pedagogical practices in Bahawalpur. There is lack of facilities and trained teaching staff as compared to private schools (Feroze, N., & Kai, Y. T. 2017)

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The term pedagogy is not a new invention; it got major attention of educationists in the 20th century where it became necessary with teaching our youths. The significance and understanding of pedagogy, which is associated to process of teaching. The instructors at any level should ensure that put practice to their teaching strategies and teaching methods in such a way that would encourage students to learn more .(Kapur, Radhika., 2020)

The term pedagogy as the Greek word for child means “leader of children” which highlights the importance of pedagogy in our educational system (Rajendra Kumar Shah, 2021) and defined as learning for its own sake whereas pedagogy is learning towards social goals. (Hinchliffe, Geoffrey., 2000)

Participatory pedagogy approach in which both students and teachers are equally accountable for learning-teaching process (Giroux, H. A. ,2010). In these circumstances the teacher is not the only one who is the source of information and knowledge; rather he involves students in dialogue process for mutual growth and development. The horizontal relationship is characterized by participatory pedagogy, which involves both teachers and children by generating two-way channels of communication. An approach will aid in the development of mutual tolerance and trust with the outside school environment. (Zepke, 2013). Furthermore, it can increase the teacher's work -related quality and performances (Guerriero., 2014).

This is crucial for private schools in the educational system, particularly in mega-cities like Bahawalpur, because of cultural concerns or more career options for the teachers, effects on education and finances are also contributing factors. This issue has drawn the attention of many researchers and practicing managers due to the rising tendency of launching new schools in the private sector and the current climate of fierce competition in the education sector. To determine the elements contributing to teachers' perceived turnover, the majority of investigations have utilized segmented approaches that take into account teacher work career satisfaction, teacher well-being, internal social factors like pressure and stress, and policy-related issues. The loss of expertise from seasoned staff due to high teacher turnover is a subject of worry for all prominent educational institutions. Researchers concluded that consequences of dissatisfaction in job and workload are physical and mental health problems, such as stress, stiff muscles, tension, stress, insomnia and anxiousness.

Our contribution to this study is examined factors that influence quality of pedagogical practices in private and public schools. The four factors are general well-being, control at work, stress at work, and job -career satisfaction that had substantial impact. Employee churn is unfavorable for the educational sector since it interferes with pedagogical activity. Some subjects go unaddressed when a school starts to lose staff members as a result of teacher turnover. It is advised that measures be developed to stop its occurrence in private schools in the interest of the children's healthy academic development since it can be extremely detrimental to their academic achievement. It has proven that individual teacher traits affect turnover rates differently and that teachers are more likely to leave institutions where there are issues with administrative efficacy, a lack of resources, and a lack of pleasure (Ingersoll.,2001)

Teachers in private schools nowadays, like other workers, do not face the same issues that their forebears did a few decades ago because of the way that the media and the internet have changed their demands, societal trends, moral ideals, economical ethics, and other factors. Along with its obstacles, the modern era has also brought along several fresh chances. Today's workers have benefited from globalization by becoming more self-assured, well-informed, and linked to the outside world.

III. RESEARCH MODEL

The proposed model shows the relationship among Quality of pedagogy practices with independent variables (stress at work, control at work, general well i being and job-career satisfaction)

Fig 1 Framework

➤ Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were developed:

- **H1:** Job-career satisfaction (JCS) has significantly positive effect on Quality of pedagogy teaching (QPP)
- **H2:** Control at work (CAW) has significantly positive effect on Quality of pedagogy teaching (QPP)
- **H3:** General well-being (GWB) has significantly positive effect on Quality of pedagogy teaching (QPP)
- **H4:** Stress at work (SAW) has significantly positive effect on Quality of pedagogy teaching (QPP)

➤ Sampling Technique

The population of our research includes all private and public schools for boys and girls in the Bahawalpur district. There were 98 public high schools in all. In the Bahawalpur district's public schools, there were around 5702 instructors. These figures come from the 2019-22 Education Statistics report. Due to a lack of data, it was impossible to determine the number of private schools. The sample was done in two stages.

In the first stage, nine private schools and eleven public schools in Bahawalpur were chosen at randomly. In the second stage, ten school teachers were selected at random from each school.

➤ Instrument

WRQoL (Work Related Quality of life) will be rated as dependent variable and identified 4 suitable independent psychosocial variables. These 4 variables are: Job-career satisfaction (JCS), General well being (GWB), Stress at Work (SAW), Control at Work (CAW). These variables have subsequently been confirmed in other samples (Edwards, Van Laar, Easton & Kinman, 2009). The WRQoL factor subscales allow researcher and organizations to analyze the most important issues affecting the overall service quality and experience of teachers. Standard descriptive summary statistics were used to characterize teacher's population. The scores of the WRQoL structured questionnaire will be administered according to the manual (Van Laar et al.,2007). Five-Point Likert-scale responses strongly agree/agree and strongly disagree/disagree were combined as agree and disagree. The WRQoL scale was used to measure perceived quality of working life. The WRQoL is a validated 22-item psychometric questionnaire and is the most widely used instrument to assess employees'

capabilities at work, monitor employees' issues and assess employees' adaptabilities with regard to changes within system. Each item was scored on a 5-level Likert-scale. It contains questions covering 4 domains:

- General well being (GWB)
- Job-career satisfaction (JCS)
- Control at work (CAW)
- Stress at work (SAW)

Each item was scored on a 5-level Likert-scale (5=strongly disagree, 4 =disagree, 3 =neutral, 2 =agree, and 1 =strongly agree). Higher scores indicated greater perceived quality of life (Van Laar et al.,2007).

The questionnaire was composed of 22 closed ended items designed on five-point Likert scales" i.e., SA "(Strongly Agree)", A "(Agree)", N "(Neutral)", SDA "(Strongly Disagree)" and DA "(Disagree)". These five-point Likert scales were coded as: SA "(Strongly Agree)" = 1 A "(Agree)" = 2 N "(Neutral)" = 3 SDA "(Strongly Disagree)" = 4 DA "(Disagree)" = 5.

➤ Reliability and Validation of Instrument:

With the help of expert in the field of education, the instrument has been validated. To verify that the instrument was reliable, its pilot study was done with 10 of respondents and statistically assessed with Cronbach alpha of 0.8 or 80%. A value of more than 60% is required for an acceptable questionnaire to be approved. (Malhotra, 2004),

➤ Data Collection

Data collection process took two months. The tools were distributed to schools at random. The researcher personally visited the schools and asked the respondents to complete the questionnaires on the same day, however the researcher was required to return to the school two or three times a week if necessary. This resulted in a favourable outcome with a 100% response rate from the respondents. Physical copies of the tools were collected.

➤ Data Analysis

SPSS was used to organize, tabulate, and analyze the study's results. Demographic analysis and Descriptive statistics were used to analyzed the data.

IV. RESULTS

➤ **Reliability:**

Estimation of internal consistency of questionnaire survey form is done by calculate Cronbach’s Alpha. A survey of approx. 10 respondents and then repeating survey with same group or sample population later. It is greater than 0.8. 22 items of questionnaire have 0.85 reliability and it is acceptable. After collecting data, it was tabulated, organized, interpreted and analyzed. These statistical tools were used, i.e., “percentage, frequency, mean, standard deviation, Correlation, Regression and ANOVA”, was used

to analyze the data. SPSS version 19 was used to calculate “mean, standard deviation, Descriptive Analysis, Correlation, Regression and ANOVA”.

➤ **Demographic Analysis**

Table 1 shows that in the study 28% people are of age 20-30 years, 55% respondents are of age 31-40 years and others, 13% teachers are of age 41-50 years and 3% experts are of age 51-60 years.Regarding gender, 31% of female and 69% of male. Percentage of teachers of private 69% and public sector 31% are given.

Table 1 Demographic Analysis (N=250)

Variables	Options	%
Age	20-30 years	28.3
	31-40 years	55.3
	41-50 years	13.2
	51 or above	3.1
Gender	female	30.8
	male	69.2
Sector	Private	69.1
	Public	30.9
Income per month	Less than 40K	20.6
	40-50 K	8.2
	51-60 K	18.2
	61-70 K	3.3
	71-80 K	9.4
	>100K	27.0
Total		100%

Descriptive Statistics table 2 of working experience shows significant results as it is shown in Table 2 that N Statistic is 250, Minimum Statistic is 3, Maximum Statistic is 36, Mean Statistic is 8.21, Std. Deviation is 6.1844.

This Descriptive Statistics table 2 of working hours shows significant results as it is shown in table that N Statistic is 250, Minimum Statistic is 6.1, Maximum Statistic is 24, Mean Statistic is 41.48, Std. Deviation is 28.777.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics of work

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Work experience	250	4.3	36.0	8.214	6.1884
Working Hours	250	6.1	24	41.48	28.777

This Descriptive Statistics table 2 shows, N, Minimum, Maximum, Mean, Std. Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis of all dependent and independent variables. Job-career satisfaction (JCS), General well i being (GWB), Stress at Work (SAW), Control at Work (CAW), are independent variables and QPP is dependent variable.

➤ **Correlation:**

Correlation is used as statistical technique indicating the degree to which two variables move in conjunction. When two variables are moving in the same direction, those variables are said to have a positive correlation. A negative correlation exists when the two variables move in opposing directions. Correlation is a bivariate study that quantifies the strength of association between two variables and the direction of the relationship. In terms of the strength of the relationship, the value of the correlation coefficient fluctuates between +1 and -1. An association value of 1 means that the two variables are completely unrelated. One value's relationship with another will deteriorate as the correlation coefficient variables zero. The coefficient sign denotes the direction of the relationship; a + sign indicates a positive relationship, and a – sign indicates a negative relationship. See Table 3.

Table 3 Correlation

		JCS	CAW	GWB	SAW	QPP
JCS	Pearson Correlation	1	.557**	.583**	.174	.115
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.083	.253
	N	250	250	250	250	250

CAW	Pearson Correlation	.557**	1	.382**	.381**	.117
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.247
	N	250	250	250	250	250
GWB	Pearson Correlation	.583**	.382**	1	.022	.427**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.828	.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250
SAW	Pearson Correlation	.174	.381**	.022	1	-.082
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.083	.000	.828		.415
	N	250	250	250	250	250
QPP	Pearson Correlation	.115	.117	.427**	-.082	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.253	.247	.000	.415	
	N	250	250	250	250	250

In this Pearson Correlation table 4, p-values and coefficients in correlation analysis work together to inform you whether relationships in your model are statistically significant and the nature of those relationships. Calculate the mathematical link between each independent variable and its dependent variable using coefficients. The p-values for the coefficients reflect whether these relationships are statistically significant.

Table 4 P-Values and Coefficients

		QPP	JCS	CAW	GWB	SAW
Pearson Correlation	QPP	1.000	.115	.117	.427	-.082
	JCS	.115	1.000	.557	.583	.174
	CAW	.117	.557	1.000	.382	.381
	GWB	.427	.583	.382	1.000	.022
	SAW	-.082	.174	.381	.022	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	QPP		.127	.124	.000	.207
	JCS	.127		.000	.000	.041
	CAW	.124	.000		.000	.000
	GWB	.000	.000	.000		.414
	SAW	.207	.041	.000	.414	
N	QPP	250	250	250	250	250
	JCS	250	250	250	250	250
	CAW	250	250	250	250	250
	GWB	250	250	250	250	250
	SAW	250	250	250	250	250

➤ *Regression Analysis*

In this Regression Analysis Descriptive Statistics table 5, mean of variables QPP is 3.65, JCS is 3.6333, CAW is 3.569999, GWB is 3.5649999, and SAW is 3.205. Std. Deviation of variables QPP is 1.250, JCS is .5463273773, CAW is .91905, GWB is .626256, and SAW is 1.1593.

Table 5 Regression Analysis Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
QPP	3.65	1.250	250
JCS	3.613	.546	250
CAW	3.5699	.9190	250
GWB	3.5649	.6262	250
SAW	3.205	1.1593	250

Inferential statistics include regression analysis. Using p-values, you may determine whether the associations you see in your sample are also present in the whole population. If there is no correlation between any two independent variables, then their p-values are zero. If there is no correlation, there is no link between the changes in the independent variable and the shifts in the dependent variable. To put it another way, there isn't enough data to conclude that there is a population impact.

➤ Relationship between JCS and QPP

Table 6 Variables (JCS & QPP) Entered/Removed

Variables Entered/Removed			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	JCS ^b	.	Enter
a. Dependent Variable: QPP			
b. All requested variables entered.			

Table 7 JCS Model Summary

Model Summary ^b									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.115 ^a	.013	.003	1.248	.013	1.321	1	98	.253
a. Predictors: (Constant), JCS									
b. Dependent Variable: QPP									

In this JCS Model summary table 7, R is .115, R Square is .013, Adjusted R Square is .003, Std. Error of the Estimate 1.248, R Square Change is .013, F Change is 1.321, df1 is 1, df2 is 98 and Sig. F Change is .253.

Table 8 JCS ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.059	1	2.059	1.321	.253 ^b
	Residual	152.691	98	1.558		
	Total	154.750	99			
a. Dependent Variable: QPP						
b. Predictors: (Constant), JCS						

In this ANOVA table 8 JCS is independent variable and QPP is dependent variable. Sum of Squares is 2.059, df is 1, Mean Square is 2.059, F is 1.321 and Sig. .253.

Table 9 JCS Coefficients

Coefficients ^a									
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations		
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part
1	(Constant)	2.696	.839		3.213	.002			
	JCS	.264	.230	.115	1.150	.253	.115	.115	.115
a. Dependent Variable: QPP									

This Coefficients table 9 show, B is .264, Std. Error is .230, Beta is .115, t is 1.150, Sig. is .253, and Zero-order is .115.

Table 10 JCS Residuals Statistics

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	3.31	3.93	3.65	.144	250
Residual	-2.664	1.688	.000	1.242	250
Std. Predicted Value	-2.343	1.928	.000	1.000	250
Std. Residual	-2.134	1.352	.000	.995	250
a. Dependent Variable: QPP					

In this Residuals Statistics table 10, Minimum is 3.31, Maximum is 3.93, Mean is 3.64, Std. Deviation is .921 and N is 250.

Fig 2 JCS Histogram

In figure 2 Regression Standardized Residual is on x-axis and Histogram frequency is on y-axis The mean is 4.89E-17, std. Dev is 0.995 and N is 250.

➤ Relationship between CAW and QPP

Table 11 CAW Variables Entered/Remove

Variables Entered/Removed ^a			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	CAW ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: QPP
b. All requested variables entered.

Table 12 CAW Model Summary

Model Summary ^b									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.117 ^a	.014	.004	1.248	.014	1.355	1	98	.247

a. Predictors: (Constant), CAW
b. Dependent Variable: QPP

In this CAW Model summary table 12, R is .117, R Square is .014, Adjusted R Square is .004, Std. Error of the Estimate 1.248, R Square Change is .015, F Change is 1.355, df1 is 1, df2 is 98 and Sig. F Change is .247.

Table 13 CAW ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.110	1	2.110	1.355	.247 ^b
	Residual	152.640	98	1.558		
	Total	154.750	99			

a. Dependent Variable: QPP
b. Predictors: (Constant), CAW

In this ANOVA table 13, CAW is independent variable and QPP is dependent variable. Sum of Squares is 2.110, df is 1, Mean Square is 2.110, F is 1.355 and Sig. 247.

Table 14 CAW Coefficients

Coefficients ^a									
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	
1	(Constant)	3.083	.503		6.130	.000			
	CAW	.159	.136	.117	1.164	.247	.117	.117	.117

a. Dependent Variable: QPP

This CAW Coefficients table 14 show, B is .159, Std. Error is .136, Beta is .117, t is 1.164, Sig. is .247, and Zero-order is .117.

In this CAW Residuals Statistics table 4.14, Minimum is 3.29, Maximum is 3.88, Mean is 3.65, Std. Deviation is .146, and N is 250.

Fig 3 CAW Histogram

In Figure 3 CAW Regression Standardized Residual is on x-axis and Histogram frequency is on y-axis The mean is 5.38E-17, std. Dev is 0.995 and N is 250.

➤ 4.5.3 Relationship between GWB and QPP

Table 15 GWB Variables Entered/Removed

Variables Entered/Removed ^a			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	GWB ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: QPP
b. All requested variables entered.

Table 16 GWB Model Summary

Model Summary ^b									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.427 ^a	.182	.174	1.136	.182	21.868	1	98	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), GWB
b. Dependent Variable: QPP

In GWB Model summary table 16, R is .427, R Square is .182, Adjusted R Square is .174, Std. Error of the Estimate 1.136, R Square Change is .182, F Change is 21.868, df1 is 1, df2 is 98 and Sig. F Change is .000.

Table 17 GWB ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	28.232	1	28.232	21.868	.000 ^b
	Residual	126.518	98	1.291		
	Total	154.750	99			

a. Dependent Variable: QPP
b. Predictors: (Constant), GWB

In this ANOVA table 17, GWB is independent variable and QPP is dependent variable. Sum of Squares is 28.232, df is 1, Mean Square is 28.232, F is 21.868 and Sig. .000.

Table 18 GWB Coefficients

Coefficients ^a									
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations		
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part
1	(Constant)	.610	.660		.925	.357			
	GWB	.853	.182	.427	4.676	.000	.427	.427	.427

a. Dependent Variable: QPP

This GWB Coefficients table 18 show, B is .853, Std. Error is .182, Beta is .427, t is 4.676, Sig. is .000, and Zero-order is .427.

Table 19 GWB Residuals Statistics

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	2.17	4.87	3.65	.534	250
Residual	-2.737	1.974	.000	1.130	250
Std. Predicted Value	-2.765	2.291	.000	1.000	250
Std. Residual	-2.409	1.737	.000	.995	250

a. Dependent Variable: QPP

In GWB Residuals Statistics table 19, Minimum is 2.17, Maximum is 4.87, Mean is 3.65, Std. Deviation is .534, and N is 250.

Fig 4 GWB Histogram

In figure 4 GWB Regression Standardized Residual is on x-axis and Histogram frequency is on y-axis The mean is -2.23E-16, std. Dev is 0.995 and N is 250.

Table 20 Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Coefficients			Results
	beta	t	p-	
H1: JCS have positive effect on QPP.	0.115	1.150	.253	Rejected
H2: GWB has positive effect on QPP	0.427	4.67	.000	Accepted
H3: SAW has positive effect on QPP.	-.082	-.819	.415	Rejected
H4: CAW has positive effect on QPP.	.117	1.164	.247	Rejected

V. DISCUSSION

The current study averred that both Government and private schools have written statements of vision, Mission, and goal but Websites of most of the schools do not confirm the same. There is a great difference in the saying and actions of school teachers and administration (Hobbs, 2009). Stress is hardly enough in both sectors. But the public sector has comparatively better than private schools in sense of workload. Because it became easy to manage a small setup as compared to a large setup (Chinapas, A., Polpinit, P., Intiruk, N., & Saikaew, K. R. 2019). The effectiveness of administration is similar in both streams of schools and the administration of both sectors is effective for reducing work related stress and pressure. Coordination among staff is the same in both streams of schools. In both sectors, there is good enough coordination among staff. This study is helpful for teachers and policymakers equally, in designing and implementing the policy.

The study's goal was to check correlation between the teaching issues and pedagogical techniques of Bahawalpur's public and private schools. The study was conducted at random at different schools throughout the Bahawalpur area. According to the data obtained from the sample populations, all of the participants in this study (both private and public-school teaching-staff) had five years or more of teaching experience, with more than 69% of private school participants having 21 years or more of experience. In comparison to private institutions, only 18% of government instructors have a low WRQol. However, the fact that 82 % of government instructors and 66% of private school teachers have high WRQol was promising. The findings revealed a little variation in pedagogical comprehension QPP between government and private school instructors. As a result, it was deduced that instructors in government schools were more focused on pedagogical understanding than teachers in private schools, but the difference was little. Both the government and private schools in Bahawalpur city were found to be performing well. However, both types of schools have a lot of potential for growth in terms of raising quality standards of teaching.

The findings from 22 items on the questionnaire were all connected to information about pedagogical understanding in public and private schools in terms of pedagogy, the results exposed a little difference between government and private school teachers.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, some variables have an insignificant relationship, and some variables have a significant relationship because the significant level is 0.05. Some variables' value is greater than 0.05, and some variables' value is less than 0.05. Those variables with greater values are rejected, and those with values less than 0.05 are accepted.

SAW influence is high among private-sector teachers than in public female teachers have to SAW than males. CAW influence is higher among public sector teachers than private school teachers. GWB factor has the same influence on both public and private sector teachers. GWB has a high influence on both female and male teachers. JCS has a higher effect on the private sector than on public school teachers.

RECOMMENDATION

- There must be consistency in text and medium of instruction between public and private schools, which can serve to boost social positively and eliminate class distinctions or feelings of inferior complexity.
- There should be collaborative ventures between public and private schools that involve teacher trainings or student educational activities that promote general well-being among school teachers as well as a healthy teaching environment.
- An authoritative authority at the provincial level should be responsible for maintaining uniformity and quality education in both public and private schools by providing job satisfaction to instructors.

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